

Neurogenetic and neuroreconstructive homeostasis from cellular and molecular organisation of the nervous system

V. Sri Rekha^{1*}, Prof. K Eswar Kumar¹

¹A.U. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, 530003.

*Corresponding contributor:

V. Sri Rekha

Affiliation: A.U. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Andhra University, Vishakapatnam,530003.

Abstract:

Nervous system is a complex structural and functional network among the total organ systems of a living being which responds to the physical as well as chemical stimuli. Nervous system developed from the ectodermal neural epithelium or neural plate is determinatively made into these neuronal and non-neuronal cells. Neuronal cells act as structural and functional entities of the nervous system whereas non-neuronal cells behave as conduits for support and protection to neuronal cells. The existence of distinct cellular contribution in CNS facilitates a specialized neurovasculature in order to maintain the homeostatic balance. Cerebral blood flow or CBF otherwise called as perfusion is a requisite for this homeostasis. Blood brain barrier (BBB) acts as a layer that separates vascular structures from the brain cells surrounded by extracellular spaces. Unlike blood-facing (luminal side), the brain-facing (abluminal) side of BBB is constituted of microvascular endothelial cells (MECs), pericytes, astrocytes which in association with the neurones forms neurovascular unit. Both the surfaces of the BBB are enriched with protein specificities. The transport function of BBB offers different transport mechanisms for different molecules. Homeostatic mechanisms of the neurons keep them under optimal operational activity which include plasticity and regeneration. *Plasticity* is the property of cells to change themselves based on their experience whereas regeneration is the property to replicate or repair or reconstruct themselves via neurogenesis or neuroreconstruction.

Key Words: Nervous system, neuronal cells, non-neuronal cells, neurovasculature, cerebral blood flow, blood brain barrier, plasticity, regeneration, neurogenesis, neuroreconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

Organization of Nervous System

Nervous system is a complex structural and functional network among the total organ systems of a living being which responds to the physical as well as chemical stimuli. The interactions of the system with that of the others are associated with the sensory components and motor components. The sensory components are directives of the environmental senses whereas the motor components are managed by the musculature as well as glandular secretions

(Ludwig PE *et al.*, 2021). Nervous system branches out into central system and peripheral system. The central system leads on with brain, spinal cord whereas the peripheral system aids the central system with nerves that are branched out along different organs and tissues.

Brain is structurally and functionally fabricated by neuronal cells and neuroglial cells. Nervous system developed from the ectodermal neural epithelium or neural plate is determinatively made into these neuronal and non-neuronal cells which get derived from the neural plate through neural tube and collective cells of neural crest. Neurone cells are first population of cells produced from the neural tube between 4th and 20th week of embryonic development. The basic property of these young neurons is to migrate (Kwon HJ *et al.*, 2011) and grow the cytoplasmic processes as well as to form the synaptic connections with the fellow cells. Neuroglial cells which are also referred to as non-neuronal cells develop along the side of the neurone cells that project from radial glia that in turn project from the neural tube whose principal function is to guide the migration of the young neurone cells towards their specific destiny. The neural tissue undergoes induction from embryonic stem cell that develops into ectodermal germ layer by means of epithelial mesenchymal transition which further forms neural stem cells (neural tube cells and neural crest cells) which in turn develop into neural progenitor cells, intermediate progenitor cells and finally into destined cells respectively. This development occurs through processes called delamination, migration and colonization (Shyamala K *et al.*, 2015).

a) Neurone or Neuronal Cells:

Neurones since ages are considered as structural and functional entities of the nervous system that evidentially perform functions like excitation, conduction and communication. The structurally defined regions of the neurones include dendrites, soma/ cell body, axon, and presynaptic terminals.

i) **Dendrites** are believed to be the canonical structures that receive information and transmit it to axon from where the action potential is generated, propagated and specific neurotransmitter is released but in certain interneurons which are devoid of axons, these dendrites by themselves can initiate and propagate the action potential and further release the neurotransmitter in accordance with the morphology and excitability of neurons (Gaillard JM *et al.*, 2020).

ii) The **cell body** is constituted of neuronal membrane, nucleus, cyto- or neuroplasm with cytoplasmic constituents and cytoskeleton, axon-hillock.

Neuronal membrane is a flexible, nonstretchable phospholipid bilayer associated with proteins, carbohydrates and lipid rafts. The proteins exist as either integral proteins or peripheral proteins, carbohydrate chains exist as glycoproteins (carbohydrate chains + proteins) and glycolipids (carbohydrate chains + lipids) that mediate in molecular recognition and cell adhesion and lipid rafts exist as microdomains composed of cholesterol and sphingolipids. Transport across this membrane occurs by either down-hill (passive) or up-hill (active) mechanism.

The *membrane proteins* associated with neuronal membrane include ionophores (that transport ions), protein pumps (that are ATP pumps like Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase

pump), receptor proteins (that transport neuronal transmitters and neurohormones), transducer proteins (that transport via enzyme ligands), structural proteins (that form neuronal junctions like neural cell adhesion molecules/NCAMs which help not only in adhesion but also as guidance cues for neuronal development, others include cadherins, integrins), and transporter proteins (that work via electrochemical gradients). This membrane protein turnover as well as their degradation is an essential indicator of neuronal health (Jin EJ *et al.*, 2018). Neuronal membrane is also a dynamic structure that is richly compartmentalized with *microdomains* or *lipid rafts* whose interactions with ion channels are essential for the propagation of action potential (Sengupta P *et al.*, 2007). While cholesterol is essential for myelination, synapse formation and axonal regeneration in nerve injury, sphingolipids on the other hand, play their role in neural recycling (Hussain G *et al.*, 2019), neuronal and non-neuronal interactions and myelin stability (Oslen ASB & Nils JF *et al.*, 2017). Caveolae/CAVs are other kind of neural microdomains (flask shaped invaginations) that are essential for endocytosis, transcytosis, maintenance of membrane integrity and cell signaling (Parat MO *et al.*, 2009). Microdomains act as molecular scaffolds that help in localization of signal proteins so as to inflect action potential propagation, synaptic signal transmission and other cytosolic cascades (Wallace R, 2010). Lipids of neuronal membrane maintain the function of synaptic vesicle cycle through clathrin dependent and independent pathways (Lim L & Wenk MR., 2009).

Nucleus of the neuronal cell body is composed of chromatin, architectural proteins and nuclear bodies which act by epigenetic regulation (Ito K & Takizawa T., 2018). The neurodevelopmental balance is constructed by nuclear proteins (Rajarajan P *et al.*, 2016).

Cytoplasm or neuroplasm of the nerve cell acts as a suspension matrix for the cell organelle and helps in transport of the motor proteins by either steady trafficking via fast component or infrequent motion due to cytoplasmic drag via slow component that occurs mainly due to microtubule distribution and transport rate of cell organelle (Mussel M *et al.*, 2014).

In precision, **smooth endoplasmic reticulum** maintains continuity of axons by means of ER-shaping proteins through tubular network and mediates homeostatic functions like glucose metabolism, calcium storage, protein transport, lipid synthesis (Ozturk Z *et al.*, 2020).

Characteristically, **Nissl's granules** present in the cytoplasm are basophilic with electron dense particles and mediate axonal conduction and regular replenishment. They maintain the functional state of the neuron and evince chromatolysis under cell injury (Nievel J & Cumings J., 1967).

Golgi apparatus of neurone cell is involved in the storage of synaptic proteins. It participates in axon specification (Caceres A *et al.*, 2007) and maintains neuronal cell polarity by maintaining protein cargo to axons and dendrites (Chen M *et al.*, 2022). It is also observed to regulate apoptosis signaling pathways by protein regulators via proapoptotic and anti-apoptotic functions (He Q *et al.*, 2020).

Mitochondria of neuronal cells is essential for membrane excitability, signal transmission and plasticity by processing ATP production, calcium ion signaling (Kann & Kovacs., 2007), regulation of neuroinflammation (Harland *et al.*, 2020) and several other intracellular functions like cellular metabolism (Son G & Han J., 2018), neuronal homeostasis at the presynapse (Devine M & Kittler J *et al.*, 2018) and neuronal replenishment (Mandal A & Drerup CM., 2019).

Lysosomes of neurone cells act as exceptional sites for macromolecular degradation and nutrient recycling and regulates neuronal lysosome sub-cellular localization (Ferguson SM., 2019). The compartment-specific endolysosomal mechanisms are believed to regulate neuronal proteome (Kulkarni & Manday., 2018). Their recruitment in the postsynaptic sites promote synaptic plasticity (Padamsey *et al.*, 2017) whereas their presynaptic activity governs axonal retrograde flux (Wang *et al.*, 2015). Disrupted macromolecular degradation by lysosomes leads to their accumulation in endolysosomal compartments, cytoplasm or extracellular environment and may cause neurodegeneration. However, these mechanisms are regulated by master regulator, PI3K-III/Vps34 (Miranda AM *et al.*, 2018).

Cytoskeleton scaffold of neurone cell is comprised of polymeric structures namely neurofilaments, neurotubules that are respectively made of actin and tubulin which mechanically support the cell. *Neurofilaments* are class IV intermediary filament proteins of the neurones categorized as neurofilament light, neurofilament medium and neurofilament heavy (NF-L, NF-M, NF-H) types that establish axon calibre whereas GFAP is a class III intermediary filament in glial cells. They offer radial growth, stability, and optimal conduction velocity. These neurofilament proteins act as intrinsic resident proteins for the synapses to maintain the neurological status of brain and its neurones (Yuan A *et al.*, 2015). *Neurotubules* conversely, by means of kinesin and dynein type of motor proteins control the anterograde or plus-ended (soma to axon tip) and retrograde or minus-ended (axon tip to soma) trafficking (Abraham Z *et al.*, 2018).

The part of cell body from which the axon arises and is comprised of a dense granular layer under plasma membrane, cluster of ribosomes, and fascicular microtubules is **Axon hillock**.

iii) In continuation with the cell body, the efficient functioning of brain network is ensured by the so called communication cables named as **axons** and it is described that the interplay between axons and extra-axonal structures explain their differential diameters and trajectory variations (Andersson *et al.*, 2020). It is being unraveled that the correlation between the conduction velocity and the axonal diameter is important not only for exertion of different functions (Seidl AH., 2014) but also it is essential for white matter plasticity (Sampaio-Baptista & Johansen-Berg, 2017). Axons based on the lipid wrap are differentiated into myelinated and unmyelinated forms. Morphologically each axon represents the following structures: **Initial segment** that acts as an initiator of the action potential through its voltage gated channels and ankyrin/ spectrin associated skeletal proteins (Huang CY & Rasband MN, 2018). **Myelin sheaths** wrapping around the axons act as insulators to promote salutatory mode nerve conduction by means of

activation of the voltage gated sodium channels in the nodal spaces whereas these channels in unmyelinated axons are present all along the length. Myelination is regulated by axonal signaling while myelin in turn regulates the axonal impulse transmission (Stassart *et al.*, 2018). The nodes of conduction called **Nodes of Ranvier** are the non-myelinated regions of the myelinated axons that are formed and assisted by axon-intrinsic and glial-extrinsic mechanisms (Rahband & Peles., 2015). On the other hand, the intracellular signal transduction on the cytoskeletal dynamics of the axons promotes axonal branching (Kalil K & Dent EW., 2014) which ends up in to **boutons** that are either *terminaux* boutons (those forming synapse with another neuron) or *en passant* boutons (those forming synapse with neurons and/or muscle fibers) which play their instance in synaptogenesis (Dan D *et al.*, 2006). Axonal transport relying on the conduction velocity is either fast or slow and based on the mode of transport is anterograde (Guillaud L *et al.*, 2020) or retrograde (Hung C *et al.*, 2021) as notified earlier.

b) Non-neurone (or) Neuroglial cells

At the structural and functional vantage with neurone cells, the complementary cellular structures made of delicate connective tissue so as to maintain the neural elements of the nervous system (Verkhatsky A, Butt A., 2013) are called as “non-neurone cells or neuroglial cells” as represented in Figure 1. These cells with their “*glue like nature*” behave as conduits for support and protection to neurone cells where each cell has specific functional readouts of its own (Jakel & Dimou., 2017). They constitute for about 33-66% of the total brain mass (Herculano Houzel., 2014). Non-neuronal cells involved in central system are **centroglia** and that of peripheral system are **peripheroglia**.

Based on their existence, **centroglia** are further divided into macro- and microglia. Macroglia are in turn constituted of i) radial cells that are further differentiated into abundant astroglia, polydendroglia (NG-2 cells), oligodendroglia, pituicytes and ii) ependymal cells.

Astroglia contribute to the tripartite synaptic association with presynaptic and postsynaptic membranes to maintain the chemical synapse. They also maintain the water and/or ion balance along with the barrier abilities of BBB (Kimelberg HK., 2010). Dynamic signalling is the hallmark feature of astrocytes and they perform crucial functions like maintenance of metabolic and structural support for neurone cells, regulation of neurogenesis as well as brain wiring, modulation of synaptic activity and plasticity via extracellular space volume and other homeostatic mechanisms (E Dossi *et al.*, 2018). It is known that they are facilitated with characteristic expression of GFAP that classifies them into four different categories namely interlaminar astroglia (in layers I & II), protoplasmic astroglia (in layers III & IV), varicose projection astroglia (in layers V and VI) and fibrous astroglia (in white matter) which are elaborated by gene expression patterns (Vasile F *et al.*, 2017). There are two other kinds of astrocytes in cerebellum and hypothalamus by names Bergmann glia and tanycytes respectively (R Siracusa *et al.*, 2019). Any CNS insult is identified by “reactive astrogliosis” which can be elucidated in CNS disorders through loss of their normal function or gain of their abnormal function (MV Sofroniew & HV Vinters, 2010).

Polydendroglia or NG-2 cells on the other hand, are technically referred as OPCs through one gateway and have an extensive self-renewal capacity. They are

present in both grey and white matter and are characteristically expressed by NG2 proteoglycan, an alpha receptor for PDGFR α . NG2 cells help in remyelination after a potential demyelination insult (A Nishiyama *et al.*, 2014). These cells possess an intimate contact with astroglia, microglia, pericytes and myelin (Boda E & Buffo A, 2014) while the lineage plasticity of these cells is specific and diversified after injury (Son & Jin *et al.*, 2015).

Apart from astrocytes and polydendrocytes, **oligodendrocytes** are the cells that act as axon insulators due to the presence of myelin. They get matured from simple progenitor (bipolar) cells to myelin producing cells (JP Michalski & R Kothary., 2015). This myelin promotes salutatory conduction via high density voltage gated sodium channels as well as long-term axonal integrity and survival as mentioned earlier (Nave 2010a). They are known to produce trophic support and conduction velocity and add on new oligodendrocytes through oligodendrogenesis (Hughes & Stockton., 2021). Any damage in the CNS leading to oligodendrocyte death results in demyelination and impairs neuronal function by means of decelerating signal transmission (Huntemer-Silveira *et al.*, 2021).

Pituicytes likely are other kind of neuroglia that are considered as resident type astroglia of posterior pituitary which surround neurosecretory axons so as to release hormones into circulation and pituicyte-derived factors are known to be associated with neuroinflammation induced BBB breakdown (S Anabalagan *et al.*, 2018).

Neuroglia in the lateral ventricular wall of CNS are known for their yet another distinct kind of cells called **ependymal cells** representing the lining of the cerebral ventricles which are associated with cerebrospinal fluid balance, brain metabolism, waste clearance and remarkable metal ion homeostasis (MacDonald *et al.*, 2021).

In contrast to all types of macroglia, the cells that offer dynamic surveillance of brain parenchyma against infections and inflammation are called **microglia** (Wake H *et al.*, 2011). Microglial cells maintain homeostatic balance via immune-to-brain communication. An altered threshold for their activation in disease and aging is explained by a unique process called “microglial priming” (Perry & Teeling 2013). The above mentioned microglial activation is categorized into two pathways that are signified by classical M₁ state and alternative M₂ state which act as counterparts where M₁ is pro-inflammatory releasing reactive oxygen species (ROS), nitrogen reactive species (NRS), as well as cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-12) and M₂ is anti-inflammatory releasing trophic factors like tumor growth factor- β , brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) (Tang & Le., 2016) etc.

Other than centroglia, non-neuronal **peripheroglia** are also categorized into macroglia (ectodermal) and microglia (mesodermal). Macroglia are further classified into myelinated and non-myelinated Schwann cells, olfactory ensheathing glia, and enteroglia while microglia develop into satellite cells. Peripheroglia enhance neuronal cell regeneration during injury by structural support, growth factor supply and cleaning debris (Barton *et al.*, 2017).

Schwann cells originate from neural crest cells and play a compelling role in maintenance and regeneration of axons (Boliver S *et al.*, 2020). Myelinated Schwann cells ensheath larger nerve fibers and are evident with myelin markers

like P0, MAG, Gal-C and the axonal tuning is controlled by NRG1 type III signaling (Michailov *et al.*, 2004). Non-myelinated also called as Remak Schwann cells ensheath smaller nerve fibers and are identified with the expression of cell adhesion molecule L1, neurotrophic factor p75. All these markers generally are downregulated in nerve injury (Sanchez *et al.*, 2017). These cells exhibit the scope to dedifferentiate during injury and initiate the expression of genes that facilitate nerve repair (Balakrishnan A *et al.*, 2021).

Olfactory ensheathing glia just like Schwann cells perform phagocytosis and clear myelin debris and necrotic bodies but they probably differ in their cytokine responses where olfactory ensheathing glia produce lower pro-inflammatory mediators and show higher capacity for phagocytosis and cell trafficking related to Schwann cells (Nazereth L *et al.*, 2020). CNS regeneration by olfactory ensheathing glia is observed to be due to their ability to express adhesion molecules, to reduce glial scarring, to offer new axons into host nervous system, and to produce neurotrophic factors (Moreno-Flores MT *et al.*, 2002).

The astrocyte-like cells lying under the cells of intestinal epithelium are called **enteroglia**, a type of peripheroglia that richly express GFAP. Enteroglia based on their shape and location are classified into type I enteroglia (within ganglia), elongated type II enteroglia (interganglion), type III enteroglia (mucosal), and type IV enteroglia (intramuscular) (Boesmans W *et al.*, 2015). These enteroglia not only modulate neuronal cell activity (Gulbransen & Sharkey 2012) but also contribute to regulation of epithelial barrier function (Vergnolle & Cirillo 2018), proliferation and differentiation of intestinal epithelium (K Bach Ngohou *et al.*, 2010), as well as gut defense (Turco F *et al.*, 2014).

On the final classifying note are the cells derived from microglia called **satellite glia** which are known to coat sensory and autonomic ganglia (Hanani M 2010). They associate with peripheral cell bodies as a differing point with that of Schwann cells by lying in contact with peripheral axons (Hanani & Spray 2020). These cells are implicated in the neuronal cell functions and repair via lipid mediated cell communications (Mapps AA *et al.*, 2022) and they mediate neurotrophic signalling via NGF exclusively in the sympathetic circuit (Enes J *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 1. Cellular types and sub-types of nervous system

NEUROVASCULATURE

The existence of distinct cellular contribution in CNS facilitates a specialized neurovasculature in order to maintain the homeostatic balance. Cerebral blood flow or CBF otherwise called as perfusion is a requisite for this homeostasis. It is the mathematical measure of arterial blood flow rate to the capillary bed of the brain tissue which is 60 mL/100gm/min and is a linear measure of cerebral perfusion pressure (CPP) = Mean arterial pressure (MAP) – intracranial pressure (ICP). With the contribution of endothelium and astrocytes, CBF is maintained by three regulatory patterns namely: a) cerebral pressure autoregulation, b) flow-metabolism coupling, and c) neurogenic regulation (Peterson EC *et al.*, 2011). The process of maintaining a constant blood flow with respect to altering cerebral perfusion pressure is referred to as *cerebral pressure autoregulation*. The mechanoreceptors of the endothelium contribute to autoregulation via increased flow velocity (shear stress) and transmural pressure. *Flow metabolism coupling* is another regulatory pattern of CBF which is defined as the ability of the brain to maintain a match between varying blood flow with that of the metabolic activity. At resting state, the CBF is higher to the regions with energy demand and it is lower in the regions with low energy use (Sokoloff, 2013). In contrast, increase in the neural activity initiates changes in the CBF via neurovascular coupling by means of functional hyperemia in the activated areas through elevated levels of K⁺ and H⁺ ions as well as extracellular adenosine (Venkat P *et al.*, 2016). Thirdly, *neurogenic regulation* is yet another regulatory pattern of CBF which is described as the capability of the perivascular nerves to modulate the CBF. Based on the origin and the type of neurotransmitters engaged, the perivascular nerves are diversified into extrinsic nerves and intrinsic nerves. The extrinsic innervation is identified outside the brain parenchyma by trigeminal, superior cervical, sphenopalatine ganglion that carry sensory, adrenergic, cholinergic nerves respectively. These extrinsic nerves leaves the perivascular space (Virchow-robin space) and attain intrinsic nerve innervation that connects to astrocyte foot processes and further innervate into cerebral microvasculature (M. Simard *et al.*, 2003).

As expressed earlier, all these three regulatory patterns are maintained by the endothelium and astrocytes. *Endothelium* that is present like bridge between vascular lumen and surrounding tissue, facilitates different vasoactive biochemicals (Ashby JW, Mack JJ., 2021) whereas *foot processes of astrocytes* directly borders the blood vessels and thereby regulates the CBF (MacVicar BA, Newman EA., 2015). It is signified that the structural and working unit of the brain that regulates the CBF is referred to as “neurovascular unit (NVU)”. In association with the regulation of CBF, NVU also helps in the BBB maintenance and cerebral homeostasis.

Each neurovascular unit is comprised of neurone cells, astrocytes, endothelial cells, pericytes, smooth muscle cells, extravascular matrix which along with the perivascular nerves exclusively form a structural network. Along with the regulation of CBF, neurovascular unit also regulates the energy metabolism, BBB formation, and blood retinal barrier formation. NVU regulates CBF and maintain homeostasis via neurovascular or vasculoneuronal coupling (Iadecola C., 2017). Nutrients are generally delivered to neurones from blood vessels through neuroglia and wastes are delivered to the microglia or into the blood stream again through neuroglia. The control of CBF by neurone cells is direct through nitric oxide and it is indirect by glial cells through potassium channels and arachidonic acid (Attwell *et al.*, 2010). Neurotransmitter release through neuronal activity helps in maintaining the architecture of the vasculature and BBB while glial cells modulate neurotransmission and promote neurogenesis (Falk & Gotz, 2017). Other defensive cells like microglia, perivascular macrophages provide phagocytosis and inflammation (Serrats *et al.*, 2010). The basement membrane surrounding the blood vessels provide fluid transport (Morris *et al.*, 2016) whereas extracellular matrix (ECM) and perivascular basal lamina gives necessary support to the glio-vascular interface (Hoddevik *et al.*, 2020).

The ECM of the nervous system depending on the location is further categorized into three forms namely interstitial matrix, perineural nets and basement membrane. The ECM proteins in the basement membrane are secreted by endothelial and parenchymal cells of the BBB and once after they are secreted, they maintain a bidirectional relationship and thereby interact with the cells so as to maintain barrier properties. In short, BBB cells secrete exclusive ECM ligands that bind to ECM receptors (Baeten KM & Akassoglou K., 2011) and perform their specific functions. Neurovascular coupling dysfunction, death of neurone cells, gliosis, activation of microglial cells, transmigration of mural cells (pericytes & vascular smooth muscle cells) and BBB breakdown are the hallmark mechanisms that characterize the dysfunction of the neurovascular unit (Willis, 2011). Neuroglia not only are structurally linked with NVU components but they are also functionally linked by specific factors namely glial cell line derived neurotrophic factor/GDNF, vascular endothelial growth factor/VEGF, fibroblast growth factor-2/FGF2, angiopoietin-1 (Jha *et al.*, 2018). Thus neuroglia supports transmission, provides protection from excitotoxicity, regulates neuronal activity, and modulates synaptic signalling through neurogliotransmitters namely inhibitory aminobutyric acid, excitatory glutamate and cytokines (Kim *et al.*, 2020). The necessary neuronal-neurotransmitter pools are maintained by $\text{NH}_3\text{-NH}^{4+}$ ions that are derived exclusively from NVU blood vessels via glutamate-glutamine cycle (Limon *et al.*, 2021). Endothelial cells and neuroglia as a whole promote angiogenesis that can be verified with the expression of VEGF and/or TGF- 1β via Wnt signaling (Ma *et al.*, 2013) while microglia promote the process of Notch-1 signaling (Outtz *et al.*, 2011). These neuroglia and endothelial cells (Thakore *et al.*, 2021) through calcium signalling promotes vasodilation by maintaining interactions with NVU pericytes (Nortley & Attwell 2017). CNS being devoid of carbohydrate storage system is in continuous quest for the energy demand which is supplied by the blood.

Neurone cells exclusively depend on oxidative metabolism (Turner & Adamson, 2011) to receive oxygen via blood supply whereas astroglia depend on

glycolytic metabolism and store glucose in the form of glycogen to support NVU and CNS. Astroglia in specific, produce glutamate and GABA through anaplerosis, which is a process of replenishing the intermediates in a biochemical pathway (Schousboe *et al.*, 2019). A majority of glucose flux required by CNS occurs indirectly via neuroglia in the NVU and minority of it occurs directly between neurone cells and vessels (Maoz *et al.*, 2018). The lactate produced from glycolysis is taken up by neurone cells to convert it into pyruvate so as to give ATP. Astroglia are also known to supplement the neuronal metabolism by fatty acid oxidation and ketogenesis (Souza *et al.*, 2019). Astroglia of NVU also provide cytoprotection by endocytosis of toxic fatty acids produced from neurone cells (Ioannou *et al.*, 2019). Neuroglia promote the homeostatic mechanisms associated with neurotransmitters, glucose, fatty acids, L-serine for NMDA receptor function and NO for balanced functioning of NVU. In disease, the astroglia and microglia are known to initiate inflammatory cascade and release neuroinflammation specific cytokines (Karve *et al.*, 2016). Glial cells exhibit different molecular profiles and may end up in hypertrophy of NVU components (Escartin *et al.*, 2021). Conclusively, glial cells engage in NVU structure, function, maintenance as well as dysfunction (Kugler *et al.*, 2021).

Endothelial cells amplify the vasodilatory response from neurones and astroglia. Furthermore, their propagation via cellular gap junctions in retrograde mode (Sokoya *et al.*, 2006) is also managed. The endothelial cells of NVU offer homeostatic control by reduced pinocytosis, increased expression of tight junctions like claudins and occludins, and by avoiding the transport of >400 kDa weighing substances. These cells form as a unilayer of tubular blood vessels specific to the location of the vascular bed (Chico & Kugler., 2021). As a distinct feature from other locations, the endothelial cells of the cerebral vasculature are devoid of fenestrations and they have a reduced thickness (Stamatovic *et al.*, 2008).

Mural cells (pericytes & VSMCs) in contrast share the basement membrane with endothelial cells and offer homeostatic control by maintaining vascular stability, BBB function, and by providing structural support to vessels (Tong *et al.*, 2021). Pericytes are the cells that have direct contact with the endothelium and show prominent role in the structure and function of microvascular networks, one such main role is in the development and maintenance of BBB (Sa-Pereira *et al.*, 2012) The two considerable functions performed by pericytes at the BBB are upregulation of BBB-specific marker production and attachment of astrocyte end-foot processes to the blood vessels (Arumulik *et al.*, 2010). Mural cells as a response to neurovascular coupling maintain the basal rate contractility by means of contractile proteins (Mazzoni J *et al.*, 2015).

Finally, the ECM of NVU maintains the vascular integrity and confides necessary support to vessels as well as surrounding cells by comprising one-fifth of brain's volume. It constitutes proteoglycans, glycoproteins and glycosaminoglycans. It acts as an exclusive reservoir for neurotropic factors, neurosignaling molecules, and neurochemical pathways (Luca & Papa, 2016). The waste products in neural synapse are conveyed to perivenous spaces from NVU and penetrating arteries whose influx-efflux is managed by aquaporin-4 (AQP-4) water channels that are present on astrocyte end feet. The neuronal and glia processes are connected

through ECM that is exclusively composed of tenascin, hyaluronic acid (HA), chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans (CSPGs) which controls the expression of neurotrophins (NTns), MMPs and MMPs (De Luca *et al.*, 2020). ECM in association with NVU mediate structural and functional modifications of the cells by maintaining the bioavailability of the neurochemicals (De Luca *et al.*, 2018). It also maintains glymphatic regulation, a process by which cellular wastes from brain parenchyma are exchanged between CSF & ECM through NVU (Davoodi *et al.*, 2019).

BLOOD BRAIN BARRIER (BBB)

BBB acts as a layer that separates vascular structures from the brain cells surrounded by extracellular spaces. It is exclusively composed of MECs lining the microvessels (7.5 μm in diameter) (Burke *et al.*, 2014) which forms the blood-facing or luminal side of BBB. These endothelial cells are cemented together with high resistance tight junctions. The brain-facing (abluminal) side of BBB is constituted of MECs, pericytes, astrocytes which in association with the neurones forms neurovascular unit. Both the surfaces of the BBB are enriched with protein specificities. The classical properties that differentiate the brain MECs from other endothelial cells include a) expression of tight junctions, b) absence of fenestrations, c) lack of pinocytosis, d) expression of active transport mechanisms, e) few caveolae at the luminal surface, f) huge numbered mitochondria (Liebner *et al.*, 2005).

Specific junctional complexes maintain the communication between the cells as well as matrix of the BBB. There are two different cell junctions namely tight junctions, adherens junctions. *Tight junctions* are further categorized into claudins, occludins, junction adhesion molecules (JAMs), and cytoplasmic accessory proteins (CAPs) (Hashimoto Y, Campbell M., 2020). **Claudins** of adjacent brain endothelial cells form the primary seal of tight junctions. Claudin -1/-3/-5/-12 are linked with cytoplasmic accessory proteins like zonula occludens (ZO)-1+2+cingulin. **Occludins** form complex with ZO1+3+actin cytoskeleton, communicate with adjacent endothelial occludins and thereby regulate paracellular permeability. **JAM-1 and JAM-3** are two junction adhesion molecules that are exclusively expressed in neural blood vessels and are responsible for cellular adherence and monocyte transmigration. **CAPs** mediate interactions either between proteins or between proteins and lipids via transduction or transportation. *Adherens junctions* are calcium dependent and form adhesive contacts in between the cells. The homophilic interactions of these adherens junctions communicate with the plasma membranes of the neighbouring cells. These junctions not only maintain adhesion but also regulate the concentration of signalling and scaffolding proteins (Lampugnani, M.G., 2010). Typical adherens junctions include cadherins, catenins, nectins and nectin like molecules. Cadherins form their cytoskeletal interactions via catenins while nectin mediated molecules interact via afadin. Both these complexes are known to establish synaptic plasticity at the neuronal junctions. However, effective adhesion is facilitated by cadherin clusters by means of forming a supramolecular complex (Kovacs & Yap., 2008). On the other hand, nectins and nectin-like protein molecules also contribute to cell adhesion and are known to maintain cell contact mechanisms in different systems (Fournier G *et al.*, 2010).

Other than cell to cell molecules, there exist cell to matrix adhesion molecules namely matrix proteins, matrix receptors, and microfilament structures. The fact of the matter in the ECM (Frantz C *et al.*, 2010) is that **matrix proteins** are part of matrisome (Hynes and Naba., 2012) with extensive network made of laminins (for embryonic development as well as organogenesis), collagens (for tensility and migration), fibronectins (adhesion, repair, motility and embryogenesis), proteoglycans (adhesion, proliferation, regulation of other matrix proteins) and tenascins (adhesion, proliferation and cell migration) (Kular JK *et al.*, 2014; Yue B., 2014). However, an interesting validation is subjected to phenomenal **matrix receptors** named integrins which interlink the cytoskeleton with that of the cellular matrix and regulate the cellular microenvironment (Anderson LR *et al.*, 2014). Other than integrins, there are other exclusive receptors with connect either to laminins or collagens (Heino, J., & Kapyla, J., 2009). Interestingly, the **microfilament** system includes protrusive components that dictate the way of cell migration and other mechanosensing activities (Ridley AJ., 2011).

In general, transport across the BBB occurs through i) passive diffusion, ii) active transport, iii) carrier mediated transport (CMT), iv) receptor-mediated vesicular transport, v) adsorption mediated vesicular transport, vi) transport through major facilitator superfamily, and vii) immune-specific transport (Kadry *et al.*, 2020). Rapid diffusion of oxygen occurs all across the endothelium in the direction from blood to brain and that of carbon dioxide occurs in its opposite. This exchange not only maintains brain metabolism, but also maintains the necessary pH in interstitial fluid, neurons and NVU. The diffusion rate of solute particles through BBB depends on their lipid solubility which is determined by log D (partition coefficient of unionized and ionized species in the solution). The factors that contribute to transport of solute particles through BBB are molecular weight (particles < 400 Da cannot cross BBB through they have higher lipid solubility), polar surface area (> 80 Å²), hydrogen bonding (permeability of BBB decreases by 1 log magnitude as one pair of hydrogen bonds get added to the solute/drug and if > 8 hydrogen bonds get added to the molecule, then it is purely unlikely to cross the BBB). This hydrogen bonding influences the BBB permeability by increasing the free energy that is essential for the movement of molecules from aqueous phase into the lipid layer of the membrane (Gleeson MP., 2008). Technically, ‘the rule of five’ developed by Lipinski is widely used in selecting compounds targeting CNS delivery (Beneth LJ *et al.*, 2016; Lipinski 2001). The MECs of BBB are composed of efflux transporters and influx transporters (Conford and Hyman, 2005). Efflux transporters prevent the entry of substances and metabolic enzymes into brain parenchyma while influx transporters deliver nutrients, essential elements and factors that promote nutrition from blood into brain cells. An interesting example of the present day research involves Trojan horse approach that utilizes these influx transporters to hitch up the nanoparticles to brain parenchyma through BBB (Robert A Yoke, 2020). The main efflux transporters at the BBB sites are p-Glycoprotein (pGp/MDR1/ABCB1/CD243), multidrug resistance associated proteins (MRPs/ABCC1-6), and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP/ABCG2), solute carrier superfamily peptide transporters (SLC15), solute carrier superfamily SLC22 organic transporters (OATs, OCTs, OCTNs), solute carrier superfamily SLC21 transporters (SLCOs) (Stazielle *et al.*, 2015). The influx transporters at the

blood-brain interface include GLUT1, amino acid transporters, monocarboxylate transporters (MCTs), nucleoside transporters (ENTs & CNTs), peptide (SLC15), and other ion transporters (Saunders *et al.*, 2018). Several transporters at the barrier sites as mentioned in Figure 2 facilitate the transport of molecules through BBB in selective manner.

Figure 2. Functional transporters at brain barrier sites

According to the transport function of the BBB for different molecules, the important mechanisms of transport are i) paracellular and ii) trans-endothelial mechanisms. i) Paracellular mechanisms include: a) Transcellular diffusion for gases and lipophilic molecules; b) Paracellular aqueous diffusion for small and hydrophilic molecules whereas ii) Trans-endothelial mechanisms include: a) Transporter/carrier mediated exchange for glucose, amino acids, nucleosides etc, b) Receptor mediated transcytosis for proteins like transferrin, insulin etc, c) Absorptive transcytosis for positively charged plasma proteins (Gupta RC *et al.*, 2015). Any circulating molecule present in the blood could get access to the interstitial fluid of the brain either via diffusion in case of lipid soluble small molecules or via mediated transport which include carrier mediated transport CMT systems and receptor mediated transport RMT systems as referred earlier. Carrier mediated transport facilitates the transport of larger peptide molecules that cannot make use of diffusive transfer. Compounds like glucose, amino acids, carbohydrates, monocarboxylic acids, fatty acids, hormones, neurotransmitters, organic anions, amines, and vitamins with the assistance of solute family transporters take in-charge of this transfer. The selective transport of the compounds in and out of the BBB depends on the orientation of the transporters while tight junctions maintain the BBB polarity by arranging these transporters on either sides on the membrane (Abbott *et al.*, 2010). On this note, the limiting factor for the larger proteins to cross BBB via CMT is the presence of peptide linkages which is annulled by the non-specific RMT or specific AMT. In RMT, the macromolecules bind to the surface receptors and assist an endocytotic event which initiates the formation of ligand-receptor cluster. This indeed initiates caveolae formation that promotes the internalization of the ligands and receptors into the endothelial cells of BBB that finally results in the process of exocytosis (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Neuroactive peptides, growth factors and regulatory proteins

follow this RMT mode of transport. The specific molecular transfer facilitated by RMT mechanisms include the transcytosis through insulin receptor (Pardridge *et al.*, 2018) and transferrin receptor (Bien *et al.*, 2014) from blood to brain, reverse transcytosis of immunoglobulins from brain to blood (Caram Salas *et al.*, 2011), endocytosis via scavenger proteins (Srimanee *et al.*, 2016) for the uptake of low density of lipoproteins (LDLs) from blood to brain via LDLRs (Andre *et al.*, 2020) and LRP6 (Zhao *et al.*, 2016) which propose target ligands like melanotransferrins, and anigiopeps etc. The Trojan horse delivery as mentioned is a recently appreciated delivery via RMT (Pardridge WM, 2020) and it facilitates the transport of genetically engineered proteins. In contrast, AMT facilitates transcytosis of positively charged macromolecules like cationic lipids, albumin etc in similar fashion (Lu. W., 2012). Another important mode of transport is by major facilitator superfamily members (Drew D *et al.*, 2021; Quistgaard *et al.*, 2016) that help in the transfer of compounds like docosahexanoic acid (Cater *et al.*, 2021; Chan JP *et al.*, 2018). Yet another crucial transport via BBB is immune-specific transport (Marchetti & Engelhardt., 2020; Muldoon *et al.*, 2013) with its important immune processors namely T-lymphocytes (Carman & Martinelli., 2015) modulate the expression of VCAM-1, ICAM-1, MCAM, LFA-1, VLA-4 while other leucocytes modulate the expression of LAMs like E-selectin (Andreone *et al.*, 2015), activated LCAMs, etc. A mere association of junction complexes of BBB with immune-cell trafficking (Liebner *et al.*, 2018) is known to promote paracellular immune cell migration across BBB. Thus, BBB behaves as a dynamic relay center (Villabona-Rueda *et al.*, 2019) and facilitates optimal communications with the peripheral circulation corresponding to its cellular and vascular heterogeneity. BBB technically exists as a limiting factor for neurotherapeutic strategies.

HOMEOSTATIC MECHANISMS

An automated process that maintains the internal stability of the organism while adjusting it to invariably changing external conditions by means of multiple feedback mechanisms is referred to as “homeostasis” (Billmann GE 2020). Homeostatic mechanisms of the neurons keep them under optimal operational activity by means of counteracting the long-term perturbations (Harnack D *et al.*, 2015). There are two such important mechanisms one being *synaptic homeostasis* that scales down the excitatory synapses and scales up the inhibitory synapses under over-excitation and the other being *intrinsic homeostasis* that is attributed to the density) and location of the ion channels, transporters and enzymes (Turrigiano GG 2011). Neurons being inherently complex, continuously modify the synaptic and intrinsic mechanisms which shape the neuronal activity and gets shaped up by the neuronal activity correlatively (T. O’Leary and D. J. A. Wyllie., 2011). The two interesting properties that maintain homeostasis of neurons are plasticity and regeneration. *Plasticity* is the property of cells to change themselves based on their experience. These changes are engaged by chemical and electrical signals of neurons and result in new dendrite sprouting, new protein synthesis, new synaptic contacts etc. Another interesting property of neurons being the property to replicate or repair or reconstruct themselves and is technically referred to as *regeneration*.

PLASTICITY

In the CNS, a severed axon can neither be repaired nor be regrown but in PNS, dendritic damage and myelinated axonal damage can be repaired if the cell bodies remain intact, if the Schwann cells remain active and if the scar tissue does not form rapidly. Neurogenesis is confined in CNS because of the inhibitory influences of oligodendroglia, absence of growth stimulating cues, CNS myelin, and scar tissue formed due to axonal damage. The structural element of a processing brain is synapse and its plasticity. The synaptic function is indicated by synaptic elements, their expression, their structural organization, their turnover, and their reshaping capability. These are pivotal for the proper function of the central nervous system. The plastic nature of the brain can be emphasized based on the experience-based modifications that it offers by means of transmission from neural circuits, reinforcement of active synapses and synaptic pruning which are considered important for brain homeostasis (Stogsdill & Eroglu., 2017). This kind of plasticity is referred as the complex of activity dependent mechanisms that modify the synaptic transmission of neurons in terms of their strength and efficacy (Mateos-Aparicio P and Rodríguez-Moreno A, 2019). It has been revealed that oligodendroglia and microglia maintain the synaptic plasticity. Oligodendroglia promote transduction and build extracellular environment whereas microglia along with their defensive properties, provide assistance for the formation of neural niche and guidance for circuit integration and tuning through growth of axons, sprouting of dendrites and remodelling of synapse (Rodríguez *et al.*, 2019). The synaptic plasticity of a developing brain depends on the different components of ECM namely basement membrane (a boundary between endothelia and brain parenchyma), perineural nets (condensed mesh-like matrix) (Bosiacki M *et al.*, 2019) and interstitial matrix (a dense network with several ECM components) (Lau LW *et al.*, 2013) which always demand a balance in their expression for adequate neuronal function. Synthesis and proteolysis of the ECM components is known to effect the synaptic plasticity. ECM components in a developing brain facilitate neurogenesis while in adults these components are known to stabilize the synaptic structures and prevent the abnormal modeling of the synapse thereby regulating the synaptic plasticity. Perineural nets that are considered as peripheral reticulum of the nerve cells maintain the synaptic homeostasis by connecting and disconnecting the axons of one neuron with the cell bodies of the other and there by maintain activity as well as plasticity (Li X *et al.*, 2024). The highest considerable plastic nature of the brain within a life span called the critical period (from birth to 5 years) ends by the simultaneous formation of these perineuronal nets (Kwok JC *et al.*, 2011). It is by now clear that plastic nature of neural cells is highly influenced by cell constituent heterogeneity intrinsically (Charvet CJ, 2020). Other than this intrinsic influence, it is also influenced by tissue environment in general, ECM and perineuronal nets in particular (Mercier F, 2016). Plasticity is thus explained as an equity between intrinsic environment of neurons and extrinsic environment in which neurons survive. Structural plasticity allowed in immature regions like dentate gyrus in hippocampus, in subventricular zone and in the layers of olfactory bulbs (Cope EC & Gould E., 2019; Kazanis I & French-Constant C., 2011) reveals the importance of pericellular microenvironment in neuronal maturation (Coviello S *et al.*, 2021).

In the course of fetal development, cells of the nervous system are formed by three weeks post-fertilization. These destined cells form a neural tube which develops later into subventricular region. Neurogenesis completes by first six months of brain development (Clancy B *et al.*, 2001) while neural cells undergo migration after their birth via neurogenesis and gliogenesis all along the paths laid by the radial glial cells from the subventricular region to the cortex surface. The migrating cells have immense potential but once after they reach their destination they undergo maturation either by growing dendrites or by growing axons. Dendrites provide surface area for synapses while axons initiate synapse formation with the targets (Kolb & Gibb 2011). The fast growth rate of the axons compared to dendrites (Polleux F & Snider W, 2010) lays an evidence that axon influences the differentiation of dendrites and further formation of the cerebral circuits. This promotion of cerebral circuitry via synapse is referred to as synaptogenesis. The differentiation, proliferation and migration of the neural cells is necessitated by endothelin B receptors whose stimulation is known to influence vascular and neuronal development (Leonard MG *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, it is observed that enormous number of neurons and their connections form via development but the unwanted cells and their respective connections are removed by process of cell death and synaptic pruning. The final stage of development after pruning is considered as the myelogenesis which occurs through glial development. Astrogenesis and oligodendrogenesis continues throughout the life but once after the completion of neurogenesis. There are two exceptional features of the brain development, one being the presence of subependymal astroglia also called B-cells in the subventricular region which have progenitor property and the other being experience based synaptic plasticity offered by dendrites and spines which is argued for experience-expectant (early forming synapses) plasticity and experience-dependent (later forming synapses) plasticity confiding experience based neural networks which lead to brain plasticity. The generic principles associated with brain plasticity are: i) brain plasticity is multi-leveled phenomenon, ii) it is neuromorphology influenced phenomenon with varied responses to same experiences, iii) it is a region-confined phenomenon based on experience, iv) it is a time reliant phenomenon, v) it is an interactive phenomenon with respect to experience, vi) it is age-dependent, and vii) it is a cognition and behaviour interfering phenomenon. The plastic variations in the brain depend on both intrinsic and extrinsic factors and it produces both positive and negative influences. However, evidence based behavioral techniques are known to drive plasticity in positive direction (Shaffer J, 2016). In non-mammalian invertebrates cell injury initiates de-differentiation that leads to regeneration (Lange C & Brand M, 2020) but in vertebrates, reprogrammed astroglia acquiring stem-cell nature would initiate reactive neurogenesis (Gotz M & Bocci R, 2021) that does not support tissue regeneration (La Rosa C & Bonfanti, 2021). Yet another process called dematuration where differentiation of mature neurons to pseudoimmaturity and reexpression of progenitor markers takes place in postnatal development (Hagihara H *et al.*, 2019).

The essentials referred for brain plasticity by Marian Diamond, Mother of neuroplasticity otherwise called 'plastic gains' include i) newness, ii) challenge, iii) exercise, iv) diet, and v) love (Diamond M *et al.*, 1984). Plasticity of brain is known to be heterogeneous in function and is structurally recognised into three different variants namely synaptic plasticity, adult neurogenesis and neurogenesis

without division (Bonfanti, L.; Charvet, C.J., 2021) and is always correlated with neural circuitry through temporal windows that are modified via activity-based and evidence-based modifications. Firstly, synaptic plasticity referring to contacts among pre-existing neurons is considered as matured kind of plasticity. Secondly, adult neurogenesis is referred as an extended form of embryonic neurogenesis (Bao & Song 2018) via immature-like stem cell niche (Feliciano DM *et al.*, 2015). Thirdly, neurogenesis without division is referred as an indication of non-newly generated immature neurons that are represented throughout adulthood (Kempermann G., 2020) which all together show differential occurrence, location and extent over time or age (La Rosa C *et al.*, 2020; Paredes MF *et al.*, 2016) wherein age dependent plasticity is species-specific (Sorrells SF *et al.*, 2020; Sorrells SF *et al.*, 2018). Adult neurogenesis or postnatal neurogenesis is represented as a slow process for completing neural circuitry (La Rosa & Bonfanti 2021; Cushman JD *et al.*, 2021) with respect to behaviours and socio-ecological systems. Environmental stimulation is known to enhance cognition (Houillon A *et al.*, 2013) whereas enriched environment is familiar to enhance neuronal phenotypes like learning, memory and exploration (Kempermann, G., 2019). Meditation is found to influence white matter plasticity (Tang YY *et al.*, 2012) while sleep deprivation influences cognitive dysfunction by disturbing white matter integrity (Castronovo V *et al.*, 2014). Brain health is improved by physical exercise (Ryan S. M, Nolan Y. M, 2016) via enhanced cognition (Angevaren *et al.*, 2008), and immune function (Simpson *et al.*, 2012) with huge impact on hippocampus (Niemann C *et al.*, 2014) and shown to increase grey matter volume (Burzynska A. Z *et al.* 2014) and adult born neuronal health (Snyder J *et al.*, 2009). On the other hand calorie restriction is able to influence the metabolic reprogramming of the biological clock through sleep cycle (Fusco & Pani, 2013). Aged brain is referred to retain plasticity by means of interplay of activities between neural structures, their functions and their experiences (Jessberger and Gage, 2008). Thus, plasticity of brain is known to be retentive (J Hatakeyama & K Shimamura, 2019; Berg DA *et al.*, 2019), age-conservative (Snyder, J.S, 2019; Lipp, H.P, Bonfanti, L, 2016), differential (La Rosa, C, 2020), structurally scaled (Charvet CJ *et al.*, 2021) and remarkably developmental (Workman AD *et al.*, 2013).

REGENERATION OR RECONSTRUCTION

It is believed that neuronal maturation in adulthood can be reversed by understanding the key mechanisms which may facilitate the regenerative capacity of brain (Bradke, F., 2020). Regenerative processes occur either under physiological manner or under pathological manner. Physiological regeneration develops as a natural consequence and helps in maintenance whereas pathological regeneration appears as a consequence under damage and help in repair. Axonal regeneration by reconstitution of damaged cell and collateral sprouting through restoration of damaged tissue by compensation (Martino G *et al.*, 2011) are two important regenerative strategies that can be characterized by scar formation. Evidences reveal that the scar formed after brain injury is composed of cellular astroglia, macrophages and microglia along with ECM derived chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans. Astrocytes mediate resealing of BBB (Faulkner JR, 2004) and also adult neurogenesis (Ma DK *et al.*, 2005) after injury while other cells of the scar support the survival of neurons (Rolls A *et al.*, 2009) whereas over-sulfated

proteoglycans promote growth (Nakanishi K *et al.*, 2006). A well-controlled recovery response via acute glial scar formation promotes essential regeneration. The processes that promote neural regeneration and that prevent neural degeneration after injury are balanced simultaneously. Technically, regeneration along with plasticity is known to be stimulated by facilitators associated with peripheral nervous system while this stimulation is restricted by central nervous system associated brakes (Nagappan PG *et al.*, 2020). Plasticity promotes a quick functional recovery whereas regeneration by involving new neuronal connections promote a stable long-term recovery from the injury. However, this regenerative capacity has a very narrow window after injury. Ageing is observed to be a substantial interfering factor with regeneration due to impairment in the neuroglia (Painter MW *et al.*, 2014). Not only ageing but it is also evident that several factors in the CNS environment restrict regeneration. These factors further attribute to myelinated oligodendrocyte function and the glial scars. In general, the oligodendrocytes that are in regular communication with the axons survive while those oligodendrocytes that miss this communication undergo apoptosis (similar to a process that occurs in the developing brain). When axons disconnect during injury and oligodendrocytes die in the process, the myelin sheaths remain in the vicinity due to lack of clearance strategies by microglia and macrophages which hinders the process of regeneration by provoking astrogliosis and glial scar formation that further hinders regeneration. Interestingly, this glial scar being a product of injury it conversely promotes revascularization that helps in reconstruction of chemical as well as physical integrity of the cells (Anderson MA *et al.*, 2016). Recovery from brain injury via neuroplasticity starts with cortical remapping through regeneration or reconstruction that bypasses the injured areas with new circuits (Wittenberg GF *et al.*, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Nervous system is the dynamic center interacting with different systems with its sensory and motor components. The neurone cells excite, conduct and communicate while the non-neurone cells support and protect the structure and function of neurone cells. Based on the complex and distinct contribution of different cells the nervous system is supported by neurovasculature and specialized blood brain barrier. Each neurovascular unit is comprised of cells, matrix and perivascular nerves that forms a structural network to regulate energy metabolism and barrier formation. One such exclusive barrier is the blood brain barrier that acts as a relay center mediating specific transport mechanisms across the CNS. The cellular and molecular organization of the nervous system thus facilitates complex network of functions and potentially maintain the neural homeostasis by means of experience based plasticity and repair based regeneration or reconstruction arising a hope towards neurotherapeutic strategies against neurological and neurodegenerative diseases.

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